

Improving Process Yield through Manufacturing Digital Twin using Conditional Synthetic Data Engine (COSYNE)

Shantanu Chandra^{a,*}, Matthieu Duvinage^b, PKS Prakash^{a,**}, Patrick Davis^a and Sander Timmer^b

^aZS, 2nd Floor, MFAR Manyata Tech park, Phase IV, Manayata Tech Park, Nagavara, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India
^bGSK,20, Avenue Fleming, Wavre, Belgium

1 Appendix

1.1 Additional Data details

we use a total of 22 static+longitudinal variables in our experiments that are relevant for modeling the given drug’s batch progression. We construct the *static data* for conditional journey generation using mostly the previous reactor’s final state VCC condition and the raw materials used at the beginning of the current bio-reactor process. Meanwhile, we construct the *longitudinal data* using the sensor data readings of the 5000L bio-reactor. The details of the feature types of each of the variables used is summarized in Supplementary table 1.

Table 1. Time-varying as well as conditional variables (batch meta-data) used in all the experiments.

Feature used	Information type
AGIT_SEAL_PRESS	Longitudinal
DO_OUT	Longitudinal
JACKET_TEMP_VP	Longitudinal
OVERLAY_CO2_VP	Longitudinal
PRESS_VP	Longitudinal
SPARGE_AIR	Longitudinal
SPARGE_AIR_VP	Longitudinal
SPARGE_O2	Longitudinal
SPARGE_O2_VP	Longitudinal
pH_VP	Longitudinal
1250L_vcc_end	Static (conditional)
Ca Chloride Dihydrate Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Edta Ironiii Deriv Sodium Salt	Static (conditional)
Glucose Dextr Anhydrous Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Lcysteine Hydrchl Mohyd Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Mr-2 Basal Medium	Static (conditional)
Poloxamer 188, Nf/Ep	Static (conditional)
Potassium Chloride Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Sodium Bicarbonate Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Tc Yeastolate Uf	Static (conditional)
Magnesium Sulfate Hephy Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)
Sodium Chloride Usp/Ep	Static (conditional)

* Corresponding Author. Email: shantanu.chandra@zs.com

** Corresponding Author. Email: prakash.prakash@zs.com

1.2 Computation Considerations

We ran all the experiments for this work on Amazon AWS cloud using the G4dn instances (<https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/instance-types/g4/>). G4dn instances are the lowest cost most basic GPU-based instances in the cloud for machine learning inference and small scale training. G4dn infrastructure details are mentioned in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Infrastructure details of the Amazon AWS cloud G4dn instance used in all COSYNE experiments in this work.

Compute attribute	Value
vCPUs	8
Memory (GB)	32 GB
Physical processor	Intel Xeon family
Clock speed (GHz)	2.5 GHz
No. of GPUs	1
GPU architecture	Nvidia T4 tensor core
GPU memory (GB)	16 GB (14.8 GB usable)

Although it is a multi-component architecture, we have kept the data size and compute availability in mind for its practical application. We have designed it specifically to work well in low data scenarios with a very light computation footprint. The architecture does not require large amounts of data and high compute resources to perform well as compared other transformer architectures. For instance, although the GPU instance used had 15GB available memory, COSYNE even in its highest configuration tested never utilized more than 3GB of GPU. In Table 3 we provide more details of the training and inference times.

Table 3. Training (pre-training + joint) and inference times of COSYNE. *sim* refers to individual patient level simulations.

Attribute	Value
Training time calculation	
– No. of epochs (pre-training components)	2,500 (each for AE, S and T_r)
– No. of epochs (joint components)	10,000
– Training time (Total)	~ 5.5hrs
– Training time (epochs/s)	~ 0.9 epochs/s
Inference time calculation	
– No. of unique patients to be simulated (test)	250
– No. of simulations per patient	1000
– Inference time (total)	158 secs
– Inference time (ms/simulations)	~ 0.632 ms/sim
– Inference time (simulations/sec)	~ 1585 sims/s

We can see that even with a multi-component architecture and run-

ning on smallest available instance, COSYNE still trains at almost ~ 1 epoch/s while inference is also super efficient at ~ 1600 simulations/secs. This shows that the architecture can be trained and used on simple compute resources making it very practical for real-world scenarios.

Hyper-parameter tuning: The hyper-parameters used in COSYNE are standard across any typical deep learning framework, specifically GANs. Thus, there is no additional effort involved in training this framework as opposed to any other SOTA deep learning models. Secondly, to limit the hyper-parameter search space further and speed up the training phase, we have employed many known best-practices while training GANs based on existing literature in this domain (summarized here for instance: (<https://medium.com/ai-fusion-labs/training-gans-on-spatio-temporal-data-a-practical-guide-part-2-a7985689ebb9>)). The hyper-parameters in this reduced search space were then optimized using random search using a validation set.

1.3 Effect of latent dimension on AE

Figure 1. Test set AE loss (reconstruction loss) for different AE latent dimensions from 4 to 64 with resolution of 4 units.

AE struggles to encode information effectively if the latent dimension is too low. For higher latent dimension size, the AE overfits on training samples and performs poorly on unseen test set. As per the experimentation results in Fig 1 above, we have used latent dimension of 12 for the given dataset.